

Progress Report – RISE

1. General Progress of the action

1.1 Please indicate the progress of the action during the period covered by this report:

- The action has fully achieved its objectives for the period.
- X The action has achieved most of its objectives for the period with relatively minor deviations.
- The action has achieved some of its objectives, but corrective action is required.
- The action has failed to achieve critical objectives and/or is severely delayed.

1.2 Please describe the general scientific progress of the action during the period covered by this report (including by giving qualitative indicators and by describing deliverables and milestones achieved):

Work Package 1 “Project Management and Coordination” WP LEADER: SSSA

The RISE project 872384 “UNDERTREES” began in January 2020 (month 1) with the kickoff meeting, held at Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna in Pisa and articulated into 2 days (28-29 January 2020). A total of 26 people among Beneficiaries and Partners representatives attended the meeting, both physically and remotely.

This meeting served for **internal knowledge transfer**, to introduce partners and to align the different goals of UNDERTREES. More specifically, all the partners present or connected, including Third Countries were invited to present their skills, facilities, trials and research topics while the three main objectives were presented as well as the three thematic areas of the project. The work packages of the project were described, and the definition of

secondment was introduced, its general rules are described, among which the most important is that secondments build up the budget of each beneficiary.

After the kickoff meeting, an important adjustment of the UNDERTREES project has been the **Amendment** due to Covid-19 force majeure. In fact, the grant was suspended from 04/08/2020 and finally resumed in January 2022 with an extension of 18 months. After the resumption, in July 2022 the first secondments started, covering the activities planned in WP2-3-4, concurrently the implementation of WP1 has been conducted as programmed and described below.

WP1 is articulated into 4 main tasks, namely: Task 1.1 “Administrative management”, Task 1.2 “Data Management Plan (DMP) and Data Repository”, Task 1.3 “Secondment quality and ethics monitoring” and Task 1.4 “Progress reporting and evaluation” with the general aim of assuring that the project meets its objectives within budget and scheduled timescales.

Concerning the administrative management (**Task 1.1**), the activities have been conducted regularly, without any criticism: two meetings, involving both beneficiaries and partners have been organized in July and November 2022, to monitor the level of implementation of each WPs and to organize/monitor the secondments scheduled in the periods August 2022 – November 2022 (M32-M35) and December 2022 – March 2023 (M36 – M39) respectively.

All the deliverables scheduled in the period have been uploaded according to the deadlines and the milestones have been regularly achieved as detailed below:

Deliverables uploaded

- D6.1 Dissemination and Exploitation plan (DEP) [M34]
- D6.2 Project Platform [M34]
- D1.1 Data Management plan [M36]

- D1.2 Progress Report [M36]
- D3.1 Report on the methodological framework at field scale [M36]
- D3.2 Living Labs database [M36]

Milestones achieved

- MS2 Data Management plan [M36]
- MS6 Definition of methodological framework for field scale [M36]

Over the period covered by this report, and according to the scheduled deadline, the Data Management Plan has been developed (**Task 1.2**) and uploaded as first deliverable of WP1 (D1.1). This document provides details on the type of data that the project will generate, whether and how the data will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how they will be curated and preserved.

The proper implementation of the scheduled secondments has been monitored and a rescheduling of those not activated has been conducted, through with a constant interaction and communication between the coordinator and beneficiaries and partners involved (**Task 1.3**).

Finally, according to what described in task 1.4, the coordinator distributed to each secondee a questionnaire, to be filled after the secondment closure and designed to evaluate to what extents the project contributed to the following **impacts**:

- To increase the potential and future career development of staff members in the agroforestry sector and ecosystem services evaluation.
- To create new collaborations and to strengthen existing ones among academic and non-academic actors in the agroforestry sector at European and international level.

According to what collected so far, the estimation of the impact of the secondment experience on researchers and staff members ranges from good to very good.

Work Package 2 “Training and Career Development” - WP LEADER: CAWR

The main objective of this WP is to improve and expand academic and practical skills and knowledge to advance staff careers through lectures, university courses and summer schools. According to the approved project amendment, in September 2022 (26-30) the first Summer School (TSN1) took place in Pisa, coordinated by SSSA (**Task 2.1**)

The title OF THE SUMMER SCHOOL was “Agroforestry and ecosystem services toward sustainability of farming systems” and the lectures covered the following areas: agroecology, agronomy, AF system design, forage cropping systems, soil quality, ecosystem carbon balance, GHG emissions monitoring, spatial modelling and geostatistics, as per the GA (Figure 1).

19 students attended the Summer School and 2 of them, from INIAP, were on secondment at SSSA.

Feedback from school activities will be collected in January-February 2023 and the results will feed **Task 2.3**.

During secondment n° 23 (CAWR to SUA) n°39 (AFBI to SSSA) staff on secondments participated and contributed individually to courses at hosting institutions based on their skills, expertise and needs for further professional development (**Task.2.2**). In particular, an ER from AFBI gave a lesson during the Summer School in Pisa on “Global warming potential and agroforestry systems” and conducted field activities on carbon balance, while an ER from CAWR put the basis for courses in the areas of “socio-economics of agroforestry, agroforestry with livestock”, to develop together with SUA and delivered seminar with researchers from AF department. In addition, during secondment n°23, the visiting researcher supervised and evaluated MSc and PhD students’ projects and attended MSc and PhD students’ presentations on their project proposals and reviewed the presented research

proposals. Activities also included helping individual students design their respective research projects as well as discussing on near future projects and funding proposals to be jointly prepared. All these activities clearly contributed to develop new and lasting research collaborations and to achieve **transfer of knowledge** between participating organizations.

Task 2.3 and 2.4 have not started yet and are planned to be started at the beginning of 2023.

Title: "Agroforestry and ecosystem services toward sustainability of farming systems"					
SUMMER SCHOOL UNDERTREES PROJECT - SEPTEMBER 2022 PISA					
	Mon 26	Tue 27	Wed 28	Thu 29	Fri 30
09:30 - 11:00		Title: Global Warming potential and Agroforestry systems Lecturer: Rodrigo Olave	Title: Evaluation of soil degradation in Agroforestry systems Lecturer: Susanne Schnabel	Field trip to the "Parco della Maremma", Alberese GR	Title: Wrap-up on Agroforestry systems and ecosystem services Lecturer: Alberto Mantino
11:00 - 11:30		coffe break			coffe break
11:30 - 13:00		Title: Global Warming potential and Agroforestry systems Lecturer: Rodrigo Olave	Title: Evaluation of soil degradation in Agroforestry systems Lecturer: Susanne Schnabel		Participatory activity: co-design a methodological framework of ecosystem services in agroforestry systems
13:00 - 15:00	Start at 14:00	Lunch break			Lunch break
15:00 - 17:00	Title: Principles of Agroecology and Agroforestry Lecturer: Paolo Barberi	Title: Field activities on carbon balance Lecturer: Rodrigo Olave and Alberto Mantino	Title: // Lecturer: Susanne Schnabel		

Figure 1

Work Package 3 "Field research and data collection"

This WP has the objective to advance agroforestry research filling the knowledge gap about the ecosystem services (ES) generated by different farming systems in different biogeographical areas. The activities of WP3 are articulated into 4 tasks, namely: Task 3.1 "Define the methodology for ES accounting at field and cropping system level", Task 3.2 "Set up of the Living Labs database and activity coordinators", Task 3.3 "Data collection for ES assessment at field site" and Task 3.4 "Integrated multi-criteria sustainability evaluation of field sites".

During the Summer School held in September in Pisa (WP2), the methodology for the assessment of ES at field scale has been defined and the relative deliverable has been produced (**Task 3.1**).

In **Task 3.2** a database with the information for each identified living lab has been designed and filled in. This dataset will be used in Task 3.3 to plan the data collection, in Task 4.2 and 4.3 for the land use and ecosystem modelling and for the multi-actor participatory ES assessment in WP5.

Finally, during the first set of secondments, data have been collected to perform the assessment programmed in Task 3.3. In particular, during secondments n°29 and n°31, two ESRs from the Universidad de Extremadura (UEX) visited for 1 month each the Universidad de Concepción (UDEC) where field sampling were carried out to analyse dendrochronological features of trees located in native forest under different agroforestry management systems and some measurements were taken to determine the age of the trees and to estimate the canopy cover of the plots under silvopastoral management.

Work Package 4 “Mapping and Modelling” - WP Leader: UEX

WP4 deals with the assessment of ecosystem services of agroforestry (AF) systems at the landscape or regional scale. It is divided into the following four tasks: Task 4.1 “Definition of the methodology for ES assessment at landscape scale”, Task 4.2 “Agro-environmental modelling for ES assessment”, Task 4.3 “Socio-economic modelling for ES assessment”, Task 4.4 “Integrated sustainability evaluation at landscape scale”.

Task 4.1 deals with the development of the methodology for ES assessment which will be applied in subsequent tasks, and it is the work currently been carried out. It is based on the methodology which was elaborated for ES assessment at the field scale in WP3. A careful analysis must be carried out to define the way the field-scale methodological approaches can be upscaled and how obtained results can be extrapolated to the landscape scale. Furthermore, the usefulness of existing freely available databases, such as those from COPERNICUS in Europe, needs to be analysed. Another subject is ES assessment at landscape scale of UNDERTREES partner countries, not belonging to the EU. This will be dealt with during secondments in which UEX is participating. In fact, in the framework of WP4, two secondments were carried out so far, namely n°28 and n°30. Two ESRs spent 1 month each

in Chile at Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile (PUC) dealing with the modelling and generation of cartography on different indicators for the characterization and evaluation of agroforestry systems. During these secondments, intensive desk work was carried out, establishing a proper workflow between the two teams (UEX and PUC) for the subsequent modelling work on the previously recorded data. All this analysis work and predictive models' creation, as well as the subsequent mapping, is now in the writing stage to be sent in paper format to international journals. In addition, the collaborative work will be shared with the entire team that makes up the UNDERTREES project with the aim of continuing to improve in the search for a clear and efficient methodology.

These experiences consistently contributed to build up a methodology able to go beyond biophysical and monetary evaluation towards a common method for ES assessment at various temporal and spatial scales, thus significantly demonstrating the **added value of the project** in relation to the state of the art.

During February 2023 a specific WP4 online meeting will be celebrated in which all partners (CAWR, USC, VEX, AFBI, UEX) from this WP will participate, in order to finalize task 4.1 and to define future work of the three remaining tasks.

Work Package 5 “Participatory approach” – WP LEADER: USC

The WP5 focuses on the engagement of key actors in the agroforestry sector to identify barriers but also drivers for a sustainable development of agroforestry, considering agro-environmental, socio-economic and policy aspects. This WP has four tasks. Task 5.1 “Creation and management of stakeholder networks” and Task 5.2 “Stakeholder consultation for the definition of the ES and sustainability indicators” are related to the creation of stakeholder networks and stakeholder consultation, respectively. T5.3 “Development of local action plans and participatory multi-criteria sustainability assessment” is responsible for the development of local action plans and participatory multi-criteria sustainability assessment and in T5.4 “Guidelines for EU Common Agricultural Policy development”, indications for EU Common Agricultural Policy development will be established. Performance of T5.3 and T5.4 is in part dependent on the results of T5.1 and T.5.2. Therefore, T5.3 and T5.4 have not started yet and are planned to be started at the

beginning of 2023. The other two tasks started at the beginning of the project and are still in progress. In the following paragraph, the progress of T5.1 and T5.2 are presented.

During the reporting period, WP5 has mainly worked on **Task 5.1**. In this task, guidelines for the creation and management of the stakeholder networks in each UNDERTRES country were established by the USC and circulated among the partners. Following these guidelines, partners collected the necessary data of the stakeholders in each country to create the UNDERTREES network. Moreover, letters of intent and informed consent were signed by all stakeholders included in the networks of each country considering the data management plan of WP1. All collected data from the stakeholders were stored in the secure Microsoft Teams platform, including the non-anonymised data, and will also be included in Deliverable 5.1 which will be delivered in February 2023.

Concerning **Task 5.2** USC is working on the preparation of a first survey to know the perception of the stakeholders about agroforestry and to reach the objective to discuss and identify with the stakeholders of the UNDERTREES network (Task 5.1) the main drivers for shifting towards sustainable agroforestry. USC is also organizing different workshops with the UNDERTREES stakeholders. The first workshop will probably be in May 2023. During this workshop, the results of the first survey will be discussed with the stakeholders and a second survey will be carried out to identify agro-environmental, socio-economic and political barriers/challenges related to the agroforestry systems. A second workshop will be held in June/September 2023 to do the validation/adapted priority of possible solutions to the barriers/challenges identified in the first workshop. The results obtained will be presented in the deliverable 5.2 (month 48).

Involving stakeholders to settle, map and estimate ES, will contribute to a significant **advancement in relation to the state of the art**.

Work Package 6 “Dissemination and Communication” - WP LEADER: CAWR

The aim of WP6 is to communicate project activities and results in order to raise awareness of the concepts of agroforestry systems around the world, their management and ecosystem services and their potential for climate change mitigation to a wide range of stakeholder using several methods.

WP6 is articulated into four tasks: Task 6.1: “Dissemination and Exploitation strategy”, Task 6.2: “Dissemination and communication to academic audiences”, Task 6.3: “Dissemination and communication to stakeholders”, Task 6.4: “Networking with other projects on agroforestry at global level”.

Activities of **task 6.1** focused on the design and launch of the project web site and project platform and on the drafting and delivering of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

Concerning **task 1.2** one scientific article has been published:

1) Vargas, Yadira, William Viera, Alejandra Díaz, Leider Tinoco, Julio Macas, Carlos Caicedo, Marcelo Almeida, and Wilson Vásquez-Castillo. 2022. "Contribution of Agroforestry Systems in the Cultivation of Naranjilla (*Solanum quitoense*) Grown in the Amazon Region of Ecuador" *Applied Sciences* 12, no. 20: 10637. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122010637>.

Finally, the First Northern Training School has been advertised on the Facebook account of “Group of Agroecology – SSSA” (*Figure 2 - task.1.3*).

Figure 2

2. Corrective Measures

2.1 Please explain any delays accumulated in the secondments / activities / deliverables foreseen in the Grant Agreement and the measures taken to oversee them.

As already described, the proper implementation of the scheduled secondments has been monitored and a rescheduling of those not activated has been conducted, through with a constant interaction and communication with beneficiaries and partners involved.

Table 1 and Table 2 are the result of this activity of continuous monitoring on the secondments implementation, where it is clearly showed the secondments regularly implemented (in green), those postponed and rescheduled (in orange) and those anticipated (in yellow).

Secondment No.	Researcher No.	Researcher Category	Researcher Category/implemented	Sending Partner	Sending Country	Sending Country Group	Sending Sector Academic	Seconded to Partner	Seconded to Country	Seconded Country Group	Seconded Sector Academic	Starting Month	Starting Month/implemented	Duration	Duration/implemented	Work Package	Work Package/implementation	Status
36	17	ER	ER	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	6. PM (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	No	32	32	1	1	2. Training and Career Development	3. Field research and data collection	Updated
42	44	ESR	ESR	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	7. VEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	No	32	32	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		Updated
23	10	ER	ER	2. CAWR (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	13. SUA (OPE)	Tanzania	TC	Yes	33	33	2	3 (1 done)	2. Training and Career Development		Updated
131	43	ESR	Technical_staff	15. INIAP (OPE)	Ecuador	TC	Yes	1. SSSA (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	Yes	33	33	1	1	2. Training and Career Development		Updated
40	17	ER	ER	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	6. PM (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	No	34	33	1	1	3. Field research and data collection	2. Training and Career Development	Updated
134	43	ESR	Technical_staff	15. INIAP (OPE)	Ecuador	TC	Yes	1. SSSA (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	Yes	48	33	1	1	2. Training and Career Development		Updated
28	13	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	10. PUC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	35	34	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		Updated
30	14	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	10. PUC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	35	34	1	1	3. Field research and data collection		Updated
29	13	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	11. UDEC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	34	35	1	1	3. Field research and data collection		Updated
31	14	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	11. UDEC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	34	35	1	1	3. Field research and data collection		Updated
1	1	ESR	ESR	1. SSSA (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	Yes	10. PUC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	35	37	2	2	5. Participatory approach	3. Field research and data collection	Updated

Table 1- Secondments implemented in the period July 2022-December 2022 (10)

Secondment No.	Researcher No.	Researcher Category	Researcher Category/implemented	Sending Partner	Sending Country	Sending Country Group	Sending Sector Academic	Seconded to Partner	Seconded to Country	Seconded Country Group	Seconded Sector Academic	Starting Month	Starting Month/implemented	Duration	Duration/implemented	Work Package	Work Package/implementation	Status
100	34	ER	ER	12. FORIG (OPE)	Ghana	TC	Yes	7. VEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	No	31	40	1	1	3. Field research and data collection		
135	12	ER	ER	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	9. HoEF (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	No	31	41	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		
139	14	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	9. HoEF (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	No	31	41	2	2	4. Mapping and Modelling		
122	40	ER	ER	15. INIAP (OPE)	Ecuador	TC	Yes	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	31	57	4	4	4. Mapping and Modelling		
39	17	ER	ER	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	6. PM (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	No	32	32	1	1	2. Training and Career Development	3. Field research and data collection	
42	44	ESR	ESR	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	7. VEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	No	32	32	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		
81	27	ER	ER	10. PUC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	1. SSSA (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	Yes	32	44	2	2	5. Field research and data collection		
23	10	ER	ER	2. CAWR (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	13. SUA (OPE)	Tanzania	TC	Yes	33	32	2	3 (1 done)	2. Training and Career Development		
131	43	ESR	Technical_staff	15. INIAP (OPE)	Ecuador	TC	Yes	1. SSSA (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	Yes	33	33	1	1	2. Training and Career Development		
36	16	ER	ER	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	7. VEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	No	33	38	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		
99	34	ER	ER	12. FORIG (OPE)	Ghana	TC	Yes	2. CAWR (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	33	40	4	4	3. Field research and data collection		
18	8	ER	ER	2. CAWR (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	6. PM (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	No	33	57	3	3	2. Training and Career Development		
40	17	ER	ER	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	6. PM (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	No	34	33	1	1	3. Field research and data collection	2. Training and Career Development	
29	13	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	11. UDEC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	34	35	1	1	3. Field research and data collection		
31	14	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	11. UDEC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	34	35	1	1	3. Field research and data collection		
28	13	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	10. PUC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	35	34	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		
30	14	ESR	ESR	3. UEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	Yes	10. PUC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	35	34	1	1	3. Field research and data collection		
1	1	ESR	ESR	1. SSSA (BEN)	Italy	EU/AC	Yes	10. PUC (OPE)	Chile	TC	Yes	35	37	2	2	5. Participatory approach	3. Field research and data collection	
43	17	ESR	ESR	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	7. VEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	No	35	38	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		
37	16	ER	ER	4. AFBI (BEN)	United Kingdom	EU/AC	Yes	7. VEX (BEN)	Spain	EU/AC	No	35	46	1	1	4. Mapping and Modelling		

Table 2 - Secondments scheduled in the period July 2022-December 2022 (20)

As shown in the tables:

In the period July 2022-December 2022 10 secondments out of 20 took place.

4 secondments have been implemented as scheduled → 39-42-131-40

2 secondments have been postponed within the end of the year (M36) and currently ongoing or completed → 29-31

4 secondments have been postponed within the following 6 months (M37-M42) → 36-99-1-43

2 secondments have been postponed within the end of 2023 (M48) → 81-37

2 secondments have been postponed within the end of the project (M57) → 18, 122

4 secondments have been anticipated → 23-134-28-30

The delays are mainly justified by the staff changes occurred during the long period of suspension and by the consequent need to find people available to travel. Staff has changed in almost every beneficiary/partner and people eager to do secondments, at the time of the GA preparation, are no longer part of the corresponding institutions. In addition, administrative staff has changed as well, and it has implied an additional effort for the coordinator to train partners' new administrative staff and explain how to prepare and manage secondments.

Even the unexpected raise of the flight costs has been representing a challenge to correctly implement secondments.

Finally, two beneficiaries (HoEF and OVISUR) have explicitly declared the current unavailability to travel due to staff reduction and have asked to reassign their outgoing secondments, while maintaining those incoming.

2.2 Please indicate any potential risks identified and suggested approaches to mitigate them.

Risk n°5: Delay in the implementation of secondments → secondments scheduling is discussed and readjusted every 2 months with partners and beneficiaries, trying to reschedule secondments, when necessary and as soon as possible.

Risk n°10: Staff turnover → Two ER, one from SSSA and one from CAWR, both actively involved in the project, left the respective institution at the end of 2022. CAWR and SSSA are organizing a recruitment procedure to replace them.

3. Ethical Issues

Please indicate how the ethical issues have been addressed during the period covered by this report and mention all the approvals/authorisations already provided to the REA (if applicable).

During the reporting period, WP5 has mainly worked on **Task 5.1**. In this task, guidelines for the creation and management of the stakeholder networks in each UNDERTRES country were established by the USC and circulated among the partners. Following these guidelines, partners collected the necessary data of the stakeholders in each country to create the UNDERTREES network. Moreover, letters of intent and informed consent were signed by all stakeholders included in the networks of each country considering the data management plan of WP1. All collected data from the stakeholders were stored in the secure Microsoft Teams platform, including the non-anonymised data, and will also be included in Deliverable 5.1 which will be delivered in February 2023.

4. Additional information

Please indicate any additional information which you may consider useful to assess the project implementation during the period covered by this report, including management issues.

As declared in the reports post secondment filled in by seconded staff members, a continuous exchange of skills and a mutual support among the visiting technician/researcher and the hosting team have been deployed during the secondment implementation thus contributing to develop new and lasting research collaborations and to achieve **transfer of knowledge** between participating organizations.